

ISic1072

I.Sicily inscription 1072

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Modica

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140552

1. [— — — — — τῆ πρ]-
2. ὁ ὀκτῶ καλανδ[ῶ]ν
3. [I]εναρίων ἢ [μέρ]α Σε[λ]-
4. ἡνης ἐτελεύτησεν [—]
5. CYN#⁷ΡΙΟCΜΑΝΙΚΟCΙΗΜΕ
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492699

EDCS 39102227

PHI 140552

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0252 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 54.0928
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9523
- Paci, G. 2005. Iscrizioni da Cava Ispica. In Rizzo, F.P.(eds.), *Da abitato in abitato. In itinere fra le più antiche testimonianze cristiane degli Iblei.* Pisa. pp. 19-34. At no.8

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1072. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385439>